

Assessing the spatio-temporal distribution of extreme heat events in Mozambique using the CHIRTS temperature dataset for 1983-2016

Carolina Pereira Marghidanⁱ, Justine Blanfordⁱⁱ, Maarten van Aalstⁱⁱⁱ^{1,2,3},
Kiswendsida Guigma², Genito Maure⁴, Izidine Pinto^{2,5}, Julie Arrighi^{1,2,6}, and
Tatiana Marrufo⁷

¹Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation (ITC), University of Twente, the Netherlands

²Red Cross Red Crescent Climate Centre, the Netherlands

³International Research Institute for Climate and Society, Columbia University

⁴Eduardo Mondlane University, Department of Physics, Mozambique

⁵Climate System Analysis Group, Department of Environmental and Geographical Science, University of Cape Town, South Africa

⁶Global Disaster Preparedness Center, American Red Cross, Washington DC

⁷National Institute of Health, Mozambique

February 28, 2022

Summary

The frequency, duration, and intensity of extreme heat events are increasing worldwide, posing a significant threat to public health. However, these events have been largely under-reported and understudied across the African continent. Consequently, the nature of extreme heat hazards and the impacts of such events across Africa remain largely unknown. This research aims to address this research gap by characterising extreme heat events and their trends for Mozambique using the high-resolution remotely sensed CHIRTS-daily temperature data for 1983-2016. The results can be used for heat impact assessments and development of heat early warning system for Mozambique and other data-scarce regions.

KEYWORDS: heatwaves; excess heat factor; CHIRTS-daily; Mozambique; early warning system

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

As global mean temperatures continue to rise due to climate change, extreme heat events are increasingly being observed worldwide (Coughlan de Perez et al., 2018). Various studies have shown that the frequency, duration, and intensity of heatwaves are increasing, and are projected to increase in the future (Perkins et al. 2012). Extreme heat events impact many areas of society and pose a serious threat to human health and well-being, observed through excess mortality and morbidity rates (Watts et al. 2021).

1.2. Research gap

To date much of the research on extreme heat has been focused on mid-latitude and high-income countries, and most predominantly lacking across Africa (Campbell et al. 2018). Several recent studies provided evidence for heatwaves across Africa and highlight the urgent need for assessing heatwave risks and impacts (Harrington and Otto 2020; van der Walt and Fitchett 2021; Scott et al. 2017; Pasquini et al. 2020). Furthermore, as extreme heat events are largely under-reported and understudied in Africa, the impacts are simply unknown. Recent developments in remote sensing technology and methods can advance such research, including the development of the CHIRTS-daily product which presents a high-

ⁱ m.pereiramarghidan@student.utwente.nl

ⁱⁱ j.i.blanford@utwente.nl

ⁱⁱⁱ m.k.vanaalst@utwente.nl

resolution global temperature dataset which will be routinely updated in real time (Verdin et al. 2020). This study aims at filling the gap in understanding heat waves in Mozambique, a data-scarce country highly vulnerable to climate hazards (USAID 2017).

The objectives of this study are to examine (i) the spatio-temporal characteristics of extreme heat events in Mozambique with regards to heatwave number, frequency, duration, magnitude, and amplitude, and (ii) the trends with regards to each heatwave characteristic.

2. Methods and data

The CHIRTS-daily is a global remotely sensed high-resolution (5 km) daily temperature dataset developed by the Climate Hazards Center (CHC), currently available for 1983-2016 (see Verdin et al. (2020) for details on the development and validation of the dataset). This data is the first of its kind and has proved highly accurate for measuring extreme temperatures, also for data-scarce regions (Reda et al. 2021; Tuholske et al. 2021).

In order to move towards a general framework to measure heatwaves, the WMO's ET-SCI has adopted three heatwave definitions due to their advantages compared to other definitions (based off Perkins and Alexander, 2013). Using internationally agreed indices to measure extreme weather events is important to quantitatively compare heatwaves events and trends across regions. For the purpose of this study, the third definition of the Excess Heat Factor (EHF) was used which classifies heatwaves when excess heat conditions are experienced for at least three consecutive days, using both maximum and minimum temperatures. This definition considers both heatwave intensity (based on the 90th percentile calculated per grid cell), as well as acclimatization to heat (for details on the calculation, see Alexander and Herold 2016). This definition is appealing from a climatological perspective and has shown to be a useful indicator of impacts on human health (Nairn et al. 2018).

Five heatwave characteristics were calculated for each heatwave season (November – March), including heatwave number, frequency, duration, magnitude, and amplitude for the period of 1983-2016 (**Table 1**). The climatologies were obtained by averaging the characteristics per grid cell. Furthermore, annual trends were calculated using the non-parametric Mann Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator with significance computed at the 5% level (Perkins and Alexander 2013). Lastly, summaries for the four cities across Mozambique (Maputo City, Beira, Nampula, and Tete) were calculated by taking the average of the grid cells overlapping the administrative boundaries of each city. These were chosen based on their large population size as well as geographic locations, to compare heatwaves across the varying climates in Mozambique. Calculations were done using Climpack, R Software, and visualized using ArcGIS Software.

Table 1 Heatwave characteristics (Perkins and Alexander, 2013)

Index (short)	Index (long)	Description	Units
HWN	Number of heatwaves	The number of individual heatwaves per year	Number of events
HWF	Heatwave frequency	Total number of days that contribute to heatwaves per year	Days
HWD	Heatwave duration	Length of the longest yearly heatwave	Days
HWM	Heatwave magnitude	Average temperature across all heatwaves identified by HWN (<i>for EHF definition: average excess heat felt across all heatwave events</i>)	°C (°C ² for EHF definition)
HWA	Heatwave amplitude	Hottest day of the hottest yearly heatwave (<i>for EHF definition: excess heat felt on the hottest day of the hottest yearly heatwave</i>)	°C (°C ² for EHF definition)

3. Results

Heatwaves varied across the country. Since 1983, 1-3 annual heatwaves have been recorded (HWN), with a higher number of heatwaves occurring in the North and along the coast (**Figure 1a**). More days on average contributed to heatwave events (HWF) in the North compared to the South (18.5 vs 4.8 days) (**Figure 1b**). Furthermore, the longest heatwaves (HWD) were observed in the North and alongside the coastline, compared to the South (12 vs 4 days, **Figure 1c**). In contrast, the average excess heat felt across heatwave events (HWM) was highest in the South and Central Mozambique compared to the North (5 vs 0.3 °C²), as well as for the average peak excess heat felt during the hottest heatwave (HWA) (0.8 vs 11.7 °C²) (**Figure 1d,e**).

The trends for HWN, HWF show significant increases across most part of the country, with increases up to 0.17 heatwaves year⁻¹ (HWN), 1 number of days contributing to heatwaves year⁻¹ (HWF), and 0.8 days year⁻¹ for the duration of the longest heatwave (HWD). The trends for HWM and HWA are not significant for the time period analyzed in this study (**Figure 4i,j**).

Figure 1 Climatologies and trends for Mozambique 1983-2016. The climatologies are shown using the EHF definition for (a) HWN, (b) HWF, (c) HWD, (d) HWM and (e) HWA, and respectively; (f)-(i) the corresponding trends (hatching indicates trends that are statistically significant at the 5% level)

Since 1983, all cities have experienced more than 50 heatwaves (**Table 2**). Tete has the highest 90th percentile values, meaning its heatwaves are based on higher absolute temperatures. Years with a high number of heatwave events include the summer of 1997/1998 for Nampula, 2006/2007 for Maputo City, and 2015/2016 for all cities (**Figure 2**). The average number of days contributing to heatwaves was highest in Nampula (10.6 days year⁻¹) as well as the length of the longest heatwave (5.45 days year⁻¹). Yet, Tete contained the highest maximum values for those characteristics (50.9 and 16 days year⁻¹ respectively). For the HWM and HWA, highest average values were observed in Tete (7.2 °C² year⁻¹).

Figure 2 Annual heatwave events for different cities in Mozambique for 1983-2016 (left) and map with the locations (right)

Table 2 Summary of heatwave characteristics for different cities in Mozambique for 1983-2016

City*	90 th percentile (°C) ¹		Number of heatwave events (HWN)	Number of days contributing to heatwave events (HWF)	Length of longest heatwave event (HWD)	Average excess heat felt across all heatwave events (HWM)	Excess heat felt during hottest day of hottest yearly heatwave (HWA)
	<i>T_{max}</i>	<i>T_{min}</i>	<i>Total (events)</i> <i>(min-max)</i>	<i>Average (days year⁻¹)</i> <i>(min-max)</i>	<i>Average (days)</i> <i>(min-max)</i>	<i>Average (°C² year⁻¹)</i> <i>(min-max)</i>	<i>Average (°C² year⁻¹)</i> <i>(min-max)</i>
Maputo	35	27.5	51.8 (0-8.5)	7.7 (0-39.2)	5.4 (3-10.6)	2.3 (0.15-5.7)	6.3 (0.3-14.7)
Beira	35.7	26.9	70.7 (0-5.8)	8.6 (0-28)	4.6 (3-10.33)	2.2 (0.4-5)	6.4 (0.9-21.6)
Nampula	34.4	24.7	72 (0-6.5)	10.6 (0-47.8)	6.1 (3-14)	0.7 (0.06-1.8)	1.9 (0.1-5.8)
Tete	39.4*	28.8	53.6 (0-5.3)	7.6 (0- 50.9)	5.2 (3-16)	3 (0.8-8.7)	7.2 (2.1-17.3)

¹The 90th percentile was calculated by taking the average of the calculated 90th percentile over each calendar day, over the extended austral summer period (November – March)

* Numbers in **bold** indicate the highest value across the cities

4. Conclusion

The findings from this study clearly highlight the variations in heatwaves characteristics and show significant increases across a large part of the country for the number, frequency, and duration of heatwave events using the CHIRTS-daily dataset. At present, this study is the first to assess historical heatwave events and their spatio-temporal characteristics for Mozambique. Combining the outputs presented here with impact data such as mortality rates can provide evidence for the magnitude of the impact and inform temperature thresholds for early warning systems. Future research will examine intra-urban variabilities of heat, such that strategies can be developed at a city level to reduce heat risk. The data and methodology used in this study can be applied to other data-scarce countries, where research on extreme heat is highly needed.

References

- Alexander, L. and Herold, N. (2016). ClimPACT2. Indices and software. A document prepared on behalf of The Commission for Climatology (CCI) Expert Team on Sector-Specific Climate Indices (ET-SCI). , 2016, p.46.
- Campbell, S., Remenyi, T.A., White, C.J. and Johnston, F.H. (2018). Heatwave and health impact research: A global review. *Health and Place*, 53(September), pp.210–218. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2018.08.017>.
- Coughlan de Perez, E., Van Aalst, M., Bischiniotis, K., Mason, S., Nissan, H., Pappenberger, F., Stephens, E., Zsoter, E. and Van Den Hurk, B. (2018). Global predictability of temperature extremes. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(5).
- Harrington, L.J. and Otto, F.E.L. (2020). Reconciling theory with the reality of African heatwaves. *Nature Climate Change*, 10(9), pp.794–795.
- Nairn, J., Ostendorf, B. and Bi, P. (2018). Performance of excess heat factor severity as a global heatwave health impact index. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(11).
- Pasquini, L., van Aardenne, L., Godsmark, C.N., Lee, J. and Jack, C. (2020). Emerging climate change-related public health challenges in Africa: A case study of the heat-health vulnerability of informal settlement residents in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *Science of the Total Environment*, 747, p.141355. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141355>.
- Perkins, S.E. and Alexander, L. V. (2013). On the measurement of heat waves. *Journal of Climate*, 26(13), pp.4500–4517.
- Perkins, S.E., Alexander, L. V. and Nairn, J.R. (2012). Increasing frequency, intensity and duration of observed global heatwaves and warm spells. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 39(20), pp.1–5.
- Reda, K.W., Liu, X., Tang, Q. and Gebremicael, T.G. (2021). Evaluation of Global Gridded Precipitation and Temperature Datasets against Gauged Observations over the Upper Tekeze River Basin, Ethiopia. *Journal of Meteorological Research*, 35(4), pp.673–689.
- Scott, A.A., Misiani, H., Okoth, J., Jordan, A., Gohlke, J., Ouma, G., Arrighi, J., Zaitchik, B.F., Jjemba, E., Verjee, S. and Waugh, D.W. (2017). Temperature and heat in informal settlements in Nairobi. *PLoS ONE*, 12(11), pp.1–17.
- Tuholske, C., Caylor, K., Funk, C., Verdin, A., Sweeney, S., Grace, K., Peterson, P. and Evans, T. (2021). Global urban population exposure to extreme heat. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 118(41), pp.1–9.
- USAID. (2017). Climate Risk Profile: Mozambique. *USAID Climate Change Integration Support*, 2017, pp.1–5.
- Verdin, A., Funk, C., Peterson, P., Landsfeld, M., Tuholske, C. and Grace, K. (2020). Development and validation of the CHIRTS-daily quasi-global high-resolution daily temperature data set. *Scientific Data*, 7(1), pp.1–14. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-00643-7>.
- van der Walt, A.J. and Fitchett, J.M. (2021). Exploring extreme warm temperature trends in South Africa: 1960–2016. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 143(3–4), pp.1341–1360.
- Watts, N. et al. (2021). The 2020 report of The Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: responding to converging crises. *The Lancet*, 397(10269), pp.129–170.

Biographies

Carolina Pereira Marghidan is a graduate student at the Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation, University of Twente, the Netherlands. She has a large interest in global, interdisciplinary issues related to climate adaptation, disaster risk management, and urban development, and hopes to address these using spatial analysis and GIS.

Dr. Justine Blanford is a full professor at the Department of Earth Observation Science (EOS), ITC Faculty, University of Twente, the Netherlands. She has over 20 years of experience using GIS, big datasets, novel data and technologies to address a broad range of topics, in particular related to health geographics.

Dr. Maarten van Aalst is Director of the Red Cross Red Crescent Climate Centre. He is also full professor in Climate and Disaster Resilience at ITC, University of Twente and adjunct Senior Research Scientist at the International Research Institute for Climate and Society at Columbia University, New York.

Dr. Kiswendsida Guigma is a Technical Advisor at Red Cross Red Crescent Climate Centre. He recently completed his PhD with the University of Sussex on the drivers and predictability of heatwaves in the West African Sahel and is based in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso.

Prof. Genito Maure is Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Science of Eduardo Mondlane University. He completed his PhD in Environmental & Geographical Sciences at the University of Cape Town in South Africa.

Dr. Izidine Pinto is a climatologist with an interest in regional climate responses to human activities in Africa. Originally from Mozambique, he moved to Cape Town where he joined CSAG for his MSc and PhD (2015) on improving the understanding of future changes in extreme weather events in Southern Africa.

Julie Arrighi is Associate Director of the Red Cross Red Crescent Climate Centre; Senior Advisor at the Global Disaster Preparedness Center and a visiting research at the University of Twente. She is also a steering committee member of the Global Heat Health Information Network.

Dr. Tatiana Marrufo is a public health researcher, working as the Program Lead of Climate, Environment and Health program at the National Institute of Health in Mozambique. She is also the Head of Central Office of the National Observatory of Health in Mozambique.